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The "Family Children's Home" Experiment – an Alternative to Institutional Care (1984 – 1992)

Abstract: *Caring for children in need is a global issue and cause. Every country seeks effective models to implement and adapt in its social environment. An example of such an effort in Bulgaria is the creation and implementation of Family Children's Homes. This was a social experiment aimed at placing children in need within a family environment. The first of these homes was established in 1987 in Pernik, followed by additional homes in Sofia and Pleven. Inspired by foreign practices, the experiment began with the preparation and placement of children in "Family Children's Homes". Before introducing this alternative to institutional care in Bulgaria, the traditions of family orphanages in Czechoslovakia and Poland were studied. The concept of the experiment is closely resembling modern social service and protective measures such as foster care. The paper examines the emergence of family orphanages in the twentieth century as an alternative form of institutional care. It focuses on the experiment's development, set against the background of the general concept and organization of institutional care in Bulgaria. The research is grounded in fieldwork in the city of Pernik and the diary book "Hungry for Love" by Tsvetana Doneva, the director of the "First Family Children's Home" in Bulgaria.*

Keywords: *foster care; children at risk; foster parents; children's institutions.*

Childhood and child development, especially for children in need, are sensitive topics for any society. This necessitates the search for effective models and attempts to implement and adapt them in new social environments. An example of such an experiment is the introduction of "Family Children's Homes" (FCH) in Bulgaria, which involved placing children in need into a family environment. The first FCH was established in 1987 in the town of Pernik. Later, more family homes were opened in the country, in Sofia and Pleven.

The topic of this article is significant because it concerns the history of social policy related to "children at risk" and forms the basis of today's foster care system. The focus is on the Pernik's FCH because it was the only one that survived until the very end of the experiment. The others disbanded before the set end date for the experiment, and one, in the

town of Vratsa, never even opened. The primary sources for the study include fieldwork in Pernik and the diary-book "Thirsty for Love" by Tsvetana Doneva (1998), the director of the first FCH in Bulgaria. Information and commentary from local and national newspapers, such as "Sapernik," "Rabotnichesko Delo," "Dimitrovsko Zname," "Demokratsiya," "Vtora Mladost," "Trud," "Noshten Trud," and magazines such as "Zhenata Dnes," "Semeystvo i Uchilishte," "Otechestvo," reflecting the topic or containing factual data on the subject, were also used in writing this article. Materials from the television program "Preday Natatak" (2015) and personal field material collected in May 2017 in Pernik, where I met with Tsvetana Doneva's daughter and son-in-law (AEIM, a.e. 1001-III), were also included. These sources reflect the lives of the main participants in the experiment from its beginning to its end. Further work with additional sources, such as documents in the archives of the Ministry of People's Education, as well as local archives where information about the experiment may be preserved, is forthcoming. The research also references studies by Milena Angelova, who examines a similar experiment conducted between 1936 – 1938 (Angelova 2011); research by Rositsa Stoyanova (Stoyanova 2012) concerning the Near East Foundation and its activities in Bulgaria, as well as the campaign for "family placement" of children; as well as research by Anelia Kasabova on institutional care during socialism and work by other researchers on childhood and children at risk (Kasabova 2010; 2011).

The article aims to examine the emergence of a different form of care for "children in need", such as the FCHs in the late 20th century, as an alternative form of institutional care in Bulgaria. The study's primary objective then is to uncover the essence of the FCH concept, along with the difficulties encountered during the experiment and its outcomes, within a context dominated by institutional care for children deprived of parental care.

The first attempts at "foster care" in Bulgaria as a social service was a joint initiative of the American Near East Foundation, the Union for Child Protection in Bulgaria, the General Directorate of Public Health at the Ministry of Interior and National Health, and the Department of Social Care at Sofia Municipality for "placing abandoned children in families", which took place between 1936 and 1938 (Angelova 2011: 90). This was a relatively short-lived initiative and an early attempt to introduce "foster care" in Bulgaria. The main sources Milena Angelova uses include reports and surveys by the doctor and visiting nurses at the Health Advisory Station in Sofia under the American Near East Founda-

tion and documents from the archive of the General Directorate of Public Health. Her conclusions are that this short-lived initiative is an emblematic example of collaboration between several institutions. Above all, the experiment registers society's sensitivity towards a group of people who need support and to whom state policy must also show commitment. Although forgotten over time and failing to receive adequate publicity, this experiment is an example of a good attempt at finding a solution to the problem of children in need and opportunities for building a network of measures and activities that promote the standards of this type of care in other countries (Angelova 2011: 95; Stoyanova 2012).

In 1938, the representative of the Near East Foundation for Bulgaria prepared a detailed report on its progress and the results of one year's efforts. It stated that the experiment observed 23 children aged from 23 days to 6 years, who were handed over to them by the Sofia Regional Inspectorate for Public Care and the Department of Social Care at Sofia Municipality. The report, as well as the supplementary reports by the doctor of the Health Advisory Station and the visiting nurses, detailed the difficulties and problems accompanying attempt to place children in foster families over the course of the year. They pointed out lack of information about the children due to the initiative's campaign nature, which meant that some of the children were not "pre-screened", and they often had no documents. It became clear that in several cases, children were moved to another family within a year. The report also mentions the "group relocation of some children to families in Kalofer, much to the horror of the foster families". At this time, preparations were being made to expand foster care outside Sofia, and it is evident that some of the children were automatically included in the next campaign (Angelova 2011: 93-94).

This attempt to place children in foster families did not continue. A large portion of children without parental care in Bulgaria were placed in homes, some of which were state-run, while others were initiatives of societies which were also nationalized in the late 1940s. Living conditions in these homes varied, but even in well-run homes, children suffered from a lack of family environment and emotional connection. According to preserved archival materials studied by Anelia Kassabova, the conditions in institutions during the 1940s – 1950s included outdoor toilets and taps, lack of running hot water, dormitories with 20-30 beds, with some cases of two children per bed, heating problems, dampness, and more. During this period, similar living conditions were present in many family households, and even families who did not hold recognized

"need" or "socially disadvantaged" status sought ways to place their child/children in a state institution (Kassabova 2011: 96).

By the mid-1960s, the network of state institutions for children and adolescents had expanded, with initial efforts focused on health, enhancing personal and general hygiene, preventing and combating infectious diseases, particularly those with serious social implications. "The mobilization of substantial material and professional resources, the development of a health and social care system extending further into rural areas, and the medicalization of social services led to a relatively rapid decline in pre- and neonatal mortality and control of widespread infectious diseases. However, the socialist state's focus on accelerated industrialization and rapid urbanization created challenges in establishing an adequate social system for children deprived of parental care, both in terms of quantity and quality. Facility-related issues persisted throughout the socialist period, including insufficient and non-compliant buildings, expansion primarily through extensions and conversions, minimal or non-existent personal space for children, limited opportunities for sports, and supply shortages not only in inventory and fuel but also in food, medicines, toys, and educational materials. These institutions proved inadequate, unable to meet the physical, emotional, social, and educational needs of children deprived of parental care". Such are the issues the management of these homes acknowledged. Despite significant differences between the homes, influenced not only by urban-rural divides but also by the specific management and staff of educators, caregivers, and medical personnel, common 'unresolved problems' were evident (Kassabova 2010: 99-107).

A connection is evident between the practice of patronage/individual guardianship, introduced in the 1950s and expanded during the 1980s. This practice involved staff members individually taking children out of the institution – for walks, to their homes on weekends, holidays, or other occasions, or on excursions with their families. For economic reasons, this practice was extended to include not just staff, but also private citizens, who were carefully vetted beforehand. However, this system was entirely based on unpaid labor, presented as a form of "maternal care," and remained uncompensated (Kassabova 2011: 223).

Care institutions for "children at risk" or "children in need" emerged as part of centralized state policy for children deprived of parental care. Despite some achievements, these institutions soon revealed significant shortcomings. The neuropsychological development of the children lagged behind age norms, and their behavior exhibited specific

peculiarities. According to research conducted after the political changes, as deinstitutionalization took place, children from these institutions struggled to adapt to foster or adoptive families (Todorova-Lipcheva 2008: 7-8). Unlike children raised within families, these children lacked mechanisms of family socialization, missing out on observing and internalizing social roles and behavioral models within a family environment (Parvanova 2004: 137-138). For deinstitutionalization policies to be effective, an integrated approach is necessary, involving various measures: promoting family-based care for children deprived of parental care, reforming the care and child custody system, introducing early detection technologies for family problems and timely assistance to families and children, and restructuring child care institutions to create more favourable living conditions for children who cannot be placed with families (Volodina 2008: 2-7).

Family Children's Homes in Bulgaria

In 1987, the first Family Children's Home (SDD) was established in the People's Republic of Bulgaria. This initiative can be linked to the patronage/individual guardianship system introduced in "Mother and Child" homes (for children aged 0-3 years) in the 1950s. In the patronage system, "employees took a child under their care, bringing them home for holidays, weekends, or outside of working hours. The patronage was to be supervised by educators, and taking children home required written permission from the chief physician". As noted by Kassabova, "This practice likely arose spontaneously from the initiative of individual employees – there are no clear documents or archival materials. However, the system was quickly institutionalized. Recognizing the importance of personal patronage for the neuropsychological and physical development of children, and as a means of saving costs for the institution, it became a primary task in annual plans, and by the late 1970s, overnight stays were allowed (or introduced)" (Kassabova 2011: 190). With a view to boost the neuropsychological and physical development of children, and in order to save costs, in the 1980s the patronage/individual guardianship system was expanded, permitting children to be taken out not only by staff but also by pre-screened private citizens. Some directors of "Mother and Child" homes proposed other forms of care, citing the experience of "Czechoslovakia, Poland, and some capitalist countries [who used] more effective and cost-efficient" options for raising children, such as home care for pay (Kassabova 2011: 223). However, in the "Mother and Child" homes, patronage was presented as a form of "maternal care," requiring

"love and dedication," "selflessness," and thus remained unpaid (Kassabova 2011).

These developments in child institutions likely contributed to exploring the traditions of alternative types of children's homes in Czechoslovakia and Poland. The SDD experiment in Bulgaria was inspired by the experiences of these socialist countries.

The process was hampered by the economic difficulties and shortages of goods during those years. The experiment in Bulgaria can be divided into three stages: the exploratory stage, involving the study of the process, selection of children and parents, etc.; the substantive stage – placement of children in families and monitoring the project; and the final stage, involving the synthesis of conclusions about the experiment and the fate of its participants.

Preparation for the experiment began in 1984 when the Council of Ministers tasked a working group from the Ministry of People's Education, the Ministry of People's Health, the Ministry of Justice, and the Commission for Labor and Social Affairs to study family children's homes in Czechoslovakia and Poland. These two countries were selected because this type of care for children in need was widespread there (Yaneva 1987: 15). By order dated 15.11.1986 from the Council of Ministers, the then Minister of People's Education Ilcho Dimitrov mandated the start of an experiment to "organize family children's homes" in several Bulgarian cities. 'Guidelines for the organization of family children's homes' were prepared (Borisova 2006: 61).

The SDDs were intended to be part of the boarding school system of educational institutions. Numerous public and state organizations were involved: the executive committees of the district people's councils in the respective cities, along with the Ministry of People's Health, district leadership of the Fatherland Front, the Bulgarian Women's Movement, and the Dimitrov Communist Youth Union (DKMS). The experiment was supervised by the "People's Education" departments of the district people's councils. Initially, the heads of the "People's Education" departments in Sofia, Pleven, Vratsa, and Pernik were tasked with organizing one experimental family home each. Criteria were set for selecting management – "directors" of the homes and providing them with housing if necessary. If the family did not have sufficient living space, they were to be provided with suitable accommodation and funds for repairs and furnishing. Directors were preferably married, though exceptions could be made, with the requirement that they have pedagogical skills, education, and experience. While not explicitly stated, women were preferred

for the director role. Salary details and the selection process for children were also specified. The children had to be over 3 years old, have no parents, or if they had parents, they needed to have fully renounced their rights through official "Declarations of Parental Rights Waiver." For children over 7 years old, their wishes were considered, and for those over 14, their consent was mandatory. Preference was given to siblings to avoid separation (Yaneva 1987: 15-17; Valkova 1993: 138-139).

The residence designated as the "family home" had to meet certain requirements: it needed to have separate bedrooms for boys and girls, as well as spaces for children's study and service areas. The property could be state-owned or privately owned by the director, who would then receive rental payments. Conditions for undertaking repairs were specified, with funding allocated based on the number of children housed there. Additional staff could be hired under certain circumstances: for instance, if there are five children, three of whom are of preschool age, a general worker could be employed. Other specialists could also be appointed when there were significant behavioral or developmental issues observed in the children (Borisova 2006: 62). Children from the Family Childcare Homes were given priority when applying to kindergartens, schools, and recreational camps. They were exempt from fees at these institutions (Vulkova 1993: 139).

The concept of the Family Childcare Home reflects both the institutional-administrative approach typical of the existing system of social homes and the search for a new, informal form of care that closely mimics family conditions. The structure and status of the Family Home are clarified in Directive No. 10 of the Ministry of Public Education, which states: "The Family Childcare Home is a state educational institution which, through family upbringing methods and resources, provides conditions for the care and education of disadvantaged children who have permanently severed ties with their families and are deprived of parental care" (Ganchev 1988: 12). From the beginning of the experiment, its development was monitored and analyzed. Rositsa Georgieva, a research associate at the Central Laboratory of Psychology at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, notes: "The Family Home is not a family in the true sense of the word, but it can offer much for the emotional and social development of the child. Here, it's not just about meeting their needs for food, clothing, etc., but about the necessity of establishing a close emotional connection with a specific person" (Georgieva 1987: 8-9).

Initially, the experiment was planned to continue only until December 1, 1987, but was later extended by a decision of the Council of

Ministers until August 5, 1991 (the document does not mention the town of Vratsa). There was no change in the amount of funding, but provisions were made for establishing new Family Childcare Homes within the social care system (Borisova 2006: 61).

After the preparatory and research phase of the experiment, the actual organization began. Within a few months in 1987, three such family homes were established in Pernik, Sofia, and Pleven, accommodating children aged 3 to 10 years.

The first children were placed in the Family Home in Pernik at the beginning of 1987. The home was led by educator Tsvetana Doneva, a mother of a married daughter with a family. In her diary, she emotionally and meticulously describes this first day of the new home: "On January 16, 1987, Friday, I wrote in my diary, which I started keeping that day: 'Three children without parents found their home and a mother, whom they called their own, for the first time.' It can be considered their true birth date." Tsvetana Doneva kept a daily diary until the end of the experiment. It was published as a book in 1998, written in narrative form. The content is divided into three parts: "Living Story," "The Heavy Cross," and "Epilogue." The first part covers the children's first month in the Family Childcare Home, focusing on their daily life and reactions to the new environment. The second part highlights the difficult moments that followed, such as when the children began to fall ill, and the challenges they faced in adapting to a new school environment and their growing responsibilities. The third part, the shortest, discusses the difficulties faced during the early years of the transition after 1989 and the children's growth (Doneva 1998: 12).

In a local Pernik newspaper, the director described her role as more maternal than administrative: "[...] this is considered a state institution, and officially I am the Director of the Home, but from the first day, the children wanted me to be their mother" (Tsoneva 1995: 5). During my field research in Pernik, I learned that the boys from the home are still part of Tsvetana Doneva's family, despite her passing. They maintain a close relationship with her daughter, Lyubka, speaking regularly by phone, and even participated together in a television program dedicated to one of the boys. Lyubka initiated the television appearance, sensing the sadness of the older boy, Ventsislav, after her mother's death, and decided to encourage him. In the program "Pass It On," Lyubka shared how Bulgaria sought a person capable of successfully leading the experiment. Ventsislav spoke with sorrow about Tsvetana Doneva and how he came to live with another family in Stara Zagora, which had lost their

son. He also called them his mother and father. This family contacted him through Tsvetana Doneva, asking him to fill the void in their lives after losing their son. He shared that both parents passed away in 2011, but he remained close to them until the end (btv.bg).

Tsvetana Doneva and the three boys from the Family Children's Home.¹

Lyubka, Tsvetana Doneva's daughter, showed a folder containing newspaper and magazine articles about the experiment, which her family had collected over the years. According to her, her mother proved to be a very suitable person for the experiment. She had been a teacher, worked as an inspector in the Ministry of Education, and later in Pernik. In their case, the family used an apartment as their "home". Tsvetana was officially the director, with corresponding salary, while household management and daily life were strictly organized according to official records. According to Lyubka, Tsvetana took on multiple roles and managed everything herself. Together with another inspector, she personally visited orphanages to find suitable children for placement. She considered the apartment's capabilities and the children's health, as there was a requirement that they not have serious illnesses. The choice fell on two boys from the orphanage in Trun and a third from the orphanage in the village of Dren. The boys were aged 10, 9, and 7 years. These boys had not been considered for adoption because the eldest had strabismus, the middle

¹ Source: Family archive of Tsv. Doneva's daughter.

<https://www.facebook.com/CvetankaGeorgievaDoneva/photos/pb.100063707850631.-2207520000/926022724087462/?type=3>

one had a ruptured eardrum, and the youngest lacked a declaration of relinquishment for adoption since no one could provide it – his father was an alcoholic, and his mother was mentally ill (AEIM, Archive No. 1001-III from May 2017: 43-58).

The director's salary of the Family Childcare Home was equivalent to that of a Director of a Home for Children and Adolescents up to 11th grade. Increases were planned for staff with high qualifications and contributions to society. Oversight and monitoring were conducted by the District Council for Public Education, specifically by a school inspector responsible for the homes for children and adolescents in the district (Borisova 2006: 63). Each Family Childcare Home was allocated an annual budget, which included expenses for current repairs, rent, utility bills, the director's salary, and additional payments. Monthly, an advance was provided for food, clothing, cultural activities, and more. The exact amount of funding was not specified (Yaneva 1987: 15).

In the Pernik Family Childcare Home, there was no male figure, as Tsvetana Doneva was divorced, so the boys regarded Lyubka's husband as their "father". "We didn't live together with my mother, but he took on the responsibilities of sports activities – sports games, outings, etc.". Lyubka recalls that in the difficult years of the early 1990s, when the economic crisis hit the country and the home was left without state funding, they survived on supplies sent by Doneva's ex-husband from the countryside. "Even though they were divorced, he helped us. He had previously been a general director, so we had access to some scarce goods. The crisis was severe throughout Bulgaria" (AEIM, Archive No. 1001-III from May 2017: 49-52).

Soon after the home in Pernik, a similar one opened in Sofia, with an announcement of its opening appearing in the magazine "Family and School." The family of Silvana and Georgi Georgiev was chosen for this home. Children were placed with them shortly after the opening of the Pernik home. Silvana Georgieva was about 40 years old, a teacher and mother of two children, one of whom was an adult with their own family. As a motive for participating in the experiment, she mentioned that her children had grown up, and she had the necessary physical strength to care for children. S. Georgieva had experience as an educator in a home for children with intellectual disabilities. Again three children were placed in her care – Rumen, 3 years old; Emil, 4 years old; and Evgeni, 4.5 years old (Yaneva 1987: 17).

In September 1987, the third Family Children's Home (FCH) was opened in the city of Pleven. Initially, three children were placed there,

with plans to accommodate two more (Doneva 1988: 3). Information about this home is scarce in the press, except for general observations on the experiment. However, from the few publications found in "Narodna Mladezh," it becomes clear that this home was the last to be opened, benefiting from the experience gained in the first two homes – in Pernik and Sofia.

According to the publications, the results showed that the Family Children's Home had undeniable advantages over institutions such as Homes for Children and Adolescents: "The main outcomes in both families are: the children fully adapt to the new environment, they have grown accustomed to each other, their parents, and their new situation; they quickly fill the often vast gaps in their knowledge, skills, and habits related to family life; they learn discipline and order; and they successfully integrate into their new environments, such as nurseries, kindergartens, and schools" (Ganchev 1988: 12).

The daughter of Tsvetana Doneva is not aware of details regarding the other FCHs, except that they were also opened in the same year. However, she believes they failed quickly. How quickly is unclear, but it is presumed that the children were returned to the institutions from which they were taken. Thus, her mother was the first to achieve lasting results, with the children in her home "graduating" (AEIM, arch. No. 1001-III, May 2017: 43-58).

There is no evidence of an FCH in the city of Vratsa. It is only certain that it was planned to be part of the experiment, but it remains unclear why its setup was discontinued and at what stage.

From the periodical press of that time, we learn that the Family Home did not lack negative comments from neighbors: "Someone was enjoying themselves, while you bear the burden." It is also mentioned that there were others interested in working at the Family Home but declined when they realized they would have to do "menial" household work (Yaneva 1987: 16-17).

In newspapers and magazines up until 1992, there are no critical comments about the the experiment; all information was presented to readers with a positive light. Later, in the newspapers "Vtora Mladost" and "SuPernik", Tsvetana Doneva spoke about the difficulties her family faced during the political changes after 1989: "The funds allocated for the children did not change, while inflation skyrocketed". Despite the challenges, she did not return the children to the institution (Apostolova 2002b: 5; Tsoneva 1995: 6).

The experiment with about ten children placed in FCHs has not been thoroughly documented or comprehensively analyzed, and there is no information about the responsibility for its development. The preserved documents are mainly financial reports showing the funds allocated and how they were spent. There is no methodological guide for the work (Borisova 2006: 63). There was an apparent effort to publicize the experiment, emphasizing its positive aspects, but in reality, the conclusion of the project was neither publicized nor analyzed. The end of the last FCH coincided with the introduction of SOS Children's Villages in Bulgaria, a similar but different form of child care.

As part of Bulgaria's institutional policy on the care of children in need, there was a search for new models borrowed from other countries. The two officially conducted experimental projects share similarities but also have distinct characteristics. The experiment from the 1930s, which involved more children, resulted from a civic rather than a state initiative. The experiment in the latter half of the 1980s was limited, involving a small number of children, but it deserves attention. Although short-lived and following other countries' examples, these attempts are part of the history of social policy in Bulgaria. There is a noticeable campaign-like nature to the experiments and a lack of public justification for their success or failure. In the period between the two experiments, there was also a latent effort to "move away" from institutional care through the practice of patronage/individual guardianship, which was introduced as early as the 1950s and expanded in the 1980s. It is evident that the care of children deprived of parental care and residing in specialized institutions is not new to Bulgarian theory and practice. The reduction of children growing up in institutions is at the core of social policy in Bulgaria in the 21st century, specifically the gradual closure of children's homes and the promotion of foster care not only as a social service but also as a profession.

Bibliography:

Ангелова, М. (2011) Приемната грижа, наблюдение, контрол – първи опит за настаняване на сираци в приемни семейства в България (1936-1938 г.). – *Балканистичен форум*, кн. 1/2, 89-97 [Angelova, M. 2011. Priemnata grizha, nablyudenie, kontrol – parvi opit za nastanyavane na siratsi v priemni semeystva v Balgariya (1936-1938 g.). – *Balkanistic forum*, kn. 1/2, 89-97].

Апостолова, Р. (2002а) На три деца дадох обич, тройно повече получих. – *Втора младост*, № 17, 1 [Apostolova, R. 2002a. Na tri detsa dadoh obich, troyno poveche poluchih. – *Vtora mladost*, №17, 1].

Апостолова, Р. (2002) Не ми личи, но аз съм един щастлив човек. – *Втора младост*, бр. 18, 5 [Apostolova, R. 2002. Ne mi lichi, no az sam edin shtastliv chovek. – Vtora mladost, br. 18, 5].

Борисова, М. (2006) Семейните домове в България – първообраз на професионална приемна грижа. – Бюлетин издание на Фице България, бр. 9, 59-64 [Borisova, M. 2006. Semeynite domove v Balgariya – parvoobraz na profesionalna priemna grizha. – Byuletin izdanie na Fitse Balgariya, br. 9, 59-64].

Борисова, М. (2007) *Приемната грижа в кадър и перспектива*. София: Авангард Прима [Borisova, M. 2007. Priemnata grizha v kadar i perspektiva. Sofiya: Avangard Prima].

Виткова, Ек. (1995) Чиновници се гаврят с многодетна майка. – *Нощен труд* (София), № 14, 19 – 20 януари, 1 и 3 [Vitkova, Ek. 1995. Chinovnitsi se gavryat s mnogodetna mayka. – Noshten trud (Sofiya), № 14, 19 – 20 yanuari, 1 i 3].

Вълкова, Ю. (1993) Система за обществено подпомагане на деца без постоянна семейна среда в България. – Годишник на Софийския университет „Св. Климент Охридски“, Факултет по педагогика. Т. 86, с. 123-143 [Valkova, Yu. 1993. Sistema za obshtestveno podpomagane na detsa bez postoyanna semeynna sreda v Balgariya. In: Godishnik na Sofiyskiya universitet „Sv. Kliment Ohridski“, fakultet po pedagogika. T. 86, s. 123-143].

Ганчев, С. (1988) Семейно положение: МАЙКА. Семейните детски домове. Експеримента продължава. – *Народна младеж*, № 101, 30 април, 12 [Ganchev, S. 1988. Semeyno polozhenie: MAYKA. Semeynite detski domove. Eksperimentna prodalzhava. – Narodna mladezh, № 101, 30 april, 12].

Георгиева, П. (1987) Свой дом. – *Жената днес*, № 5, 8-9 [Georgiev, P. 1987. Svoiy dom. – Zhenata dnes, № 5, 8-9].

Донева, Цв. (1988а) Експериментът продължава. Белият път. – *Семейство и училище*, № 6, от юни, 3-5 [Doneva, Tsv. 1988. Eksperimenta prodalzhava. Belyiat pat. – Semeystvo i uchilishte, № 6, ot yuni, 3-5].

Донева, Цв. (1989) Паричка подхвърлена за щастие. – *Отечество*, № 326, 9 май, 21 – 22 [Doneva, Tsv. 1989. Parichka podhvarlena za shtastie. – Otechestvo, № 326, 9 may, 21 – 22].

Донева, Цв. (1988б) Директор на семеен детски дом в Перник. – *Десети конгрес на Отечествения фронт (14-16 май 1987 г.)*, заседания по сесии. Т. 2, 225 – 229 [Doneva, Tsv. 1988. Direktor na semeen detski dom v Pernik. – Deseti kongres na Otechestveniya front (14-16 may 1987 g.), zasedaniya po sesii. T. 2, 225–229].

Донева, Цв. (1998) *Жадни за обич*. София: ГАЛ-ИКО [Doneva, Tsv. 1998. Zhadni za obich. Sofiya: GAL-IKO].

Касабова, А. (2011) „Свои (?) в големия дом.“ За (не-) решените проблеми на домовете „Майка и дете“ в социалистическа България. – *Архиви на жени и малцинства*. Т. 3. Субекти на архивиране. Попова, К., Н. Муратова (съст.). Благоевград: УИ „Неофит Рилски“, 171-236 [Kassabova, A. 2011. „Svoi (?) v golemiya dom.“ Za (ne-) reshenite problemi na domovete „Mayka i dete“ v sotsialisticheska Balgariya. – Arhivi na zheni i maltsinstva. T. 3. Subekti na arhivirane. Popova, K., N. Muratova (sast.). Blagoevgrad: UI „Neofit Rilski“, 171-236].

Касабова, А. (2010) „Държавното дете“: Етатизиране на грижите за децата в социалистическа България. – *Детството при социализма. Политически, институционални и биографични перспективи*. Еленков, И., Д. Колева (Съст.): София: ЦАИ, Рива, 94-107 [Kassabova, A. 2010. „Darzhavnoto dete“: Etatizirane na

grizhite za detsata v sotsialisticheska Bulgariya. – Detstvoto pri sotsializma. Politicheski, institutsionalni i biografichni perspektivi. Elenkov, I., D. Koleva (Sast.): Sofiya: TSAI, Riva, 94-107].

Първанова, Й. (2004) Социализация и ресоциализация в специализираните институции за отглеждане и възпитание на деца, лишени от родителска грижа. – *Годишник на Софийския университет „Св. Климент Охридски“*, т. 97, кн. Социални дейности, 129-147 [Parvanova, Y. 2004. Sotsializatsiya i resotsializatsiya v spetsializiraniye institutsii za otglezhdane i vazpitanie na detsa, lisheni ot roditelska grizha. Godishnik na Sofiyskiya universitet „Sv. Kliment Ohridski“, t. 97, kn. Sotsialni deynosti, 129-147].

Тодорова – Липчева, И. (2008) *Децата в институция. Трудности в процеса на деинституционализация на децата, лишени от родителски грижи.* Варна: Сдружение „Съучастие“ [Todorova – Lipcheva, I. 2008. *Detsata v institutsiya. Trudnosti v protsesa na deinstitutionalizatsiya na detsata, lisheni ot roditelski grizhi.* Varna: Sdruzhenie „Sauchastie“].

Цонева, В. (1995) „За жалост няма инициативни хора в България“ – *Съперник*, 6 [Tsoneva, V. 1995. „Za zhalost nyama initsiativni hora v Bulgariya“ – *Sapernik*, 6].

Янева, К. (1987) Семейния дом. Тънкото равновесие. – *Семество и училище*, № 6, с. 15 – 17 [Yaneva, K. 1987. *Semeyniya dom. Tankoto ravnovesie.* – *Semestvo i uchilishte*, № 6, s. 15 – 17].

Internet sources:

Володина, Ю. (2008) Особенности деинституционализации детей-сирот и детей, лишенных родительского попечительства. Педагогика бр. 3, 16-21. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/osobennosti-deinstitutionalizatsii-detey-sirot-i-detey-lishennyh-roditelskogo-popechitelstva/viewer> (януари 2024) [Volodina, Yu. 2008. *Osobnosti deinstitutionalizatsii detey-sirot i detey, lishennyih roditelyskogo popechitelystva.* Pedagogiki br. 3, 16-21. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/osobennosti-deinstitutionalizatsii-detey-sirot-i-detey-lishennyh-roditelskogo-popechitelstva/viewer> (yanuari 2024)].

Стоянова, Р. 2012. Близкоизточна фондация. – БЛИЗКОИЗТОЧНА ФОНДАЦИЯ (daritelite.bg) [Stoyanova, R. 2012. *Blizkoiztochna fondatsia.* – *Entsiklopedia Daritelstvbo* *Енциклопедия Дарителството.* БЛИЗКОИЗТОЧНА ФОНДАЦИЯ (daritelite.bg)].

Предай нататък (тв предаване от 22. 11. 2015) <https://www.btv.bg/shows/preadai-natatak/videos/zhadni-za-obich.html> (март 2024) [Preday natatak (tv predavane ot 22. 11. 2015) <https://www.btv.bg/shows/preadai-natatak/videos/zhadni-za-obich.html> (mart 2024)].

Archival sources:

АИЕФЕМ, арх.№1001-III: (83 стр.) януари – юли 2017 г., Теренен материал събран от Хр. Башева на тема: „Приемна грижа“ в градовете София, Пловдив, Перник [АИЕФЕМ, арх.№1001-III: (83 str.) yanuari – yuli 2017 g., Terenen material sabran ot Hr. Basheva na tema: „Priemna grizha“ v gradovete Sofiya, Plovdiv, Pernik].